

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

DATABASE ON SPATIAL FEATURES AND DISTRIBUTION OF THIRD COUNTRY NATIONALS

MATILDE DELIVERABLE 2.2

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DELIVERABLE 2.2 - Database on spatial features and TCNs distribution

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CLC:	Corine Land Cover
CRS:	Coordinate Reference System
DEGURBA:	Degree of urbanisation
ESPON:	European Territorial Observatory Network
ESPON PROFECY:	Inner Peripheries: National territories facing challenges of access to basic services of general interest
EU:	European Union
Eurostat	Statistical office of the European Union situated in Luxembourg
GDP	Gross domestic product
GIS:	Geographical Information System
GISCO:	Geographic Information System of the Commission
ILO:	International Labour Organization
INSPIRE:	Infrastructure for spatial information in Europe
km:	Kilometre
LAU:	Local administrative units
OECD:	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
m:	Meter
NACE:	Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne (engl. Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community)
NUTS:	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
SGI:	Services of General Interest
TCNs:	Third Country Nationals
WP:	Work Package

1. AIM AND UTILITY OF THE MATILDE DATABASE

MATILDE Deliverable 2.2, “Database on spatial features and distribution of Third Country Nationals” (TCNs) is created by Eurac Research and FAU in Task 2.1 by combining spatial features and development characteristics of MATILDE regions. The database collects indicators of TCNs as well as three dimensions of spatial features: territorial dimension, socioeconomic dimension, and the infrastructure development dimension. The **territorial dimension** on the one hand includes data from existing analysis at European level on regional typologies. On the other hand, it provides land cover data. The **socioeconomic dimension** includes demographic data on population size, composition and population change, as well as economic data on productivity, labour market, risk of poverty and education. The **infrastructural dimension** provides data to access to Services of General Interest (SGI).

The database was used for the creation of regional profiles in task 2.1, to reach a harmonisation for the comparability of the collected data. It was needed for the classification of the MATILDE regions based on spatial specificities and Third Country Nationals distribution. The database presents a first selection of indicators to be used at the time of assessing the impact of TCNs on rural and mountain regions. The indicators presented in this database will be integrated with additional ones in Task 2.4, to define the MATILDE matrix. The MATILDE matrix will present a set of indicators to analyse social, economic and territorial impacts and serve as a starting point for subsequent analysis.

2. DESIGN OF THE MATILDE DATABASE

The overall logic behind the design of the database refers to the classification of MATILDE regions (D2.1), to answer the research question in Work Package 2 and grounds subsequent analyses in the forthcoming WPs.

The whole database consists of two parts. The first part is elaborated as a table database in EXCEL-format to calculate variables and conduct a cluster analysis for the classification of the regions, presented in Deliverable 2.1. The second part is based on technology of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and consists of a geodatabase in “.gdb”-Format, which is the starting point for the visualisation of the collected data on thematic maps (see deliverable D2.3 “Cartographic representation of MATILDE regions”).

To achieve the objective to perform a **spatial analysis of regional features**, the dataset was created using the classification “*Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques*” (NUTS) of European regions. This is a European-wide definition of regions on an appropriate scale for a comparison and with already harmonized data from different database sources (Eurostat 2020).

Although the databases are split up in two parts, it is possible to join data of the table database to the geodatabase, based on the territorial level of NUTS 3 regions. This was needed especially for the categorisation of the regions according to its total population development and the population development through migration, as well as the visualisation of TCNs distribution.

2.1 DATA COLLECTION AND HARMONIZATION

With the aim to identify which data can be concretely collected, compiled or estimated for setting up a database on spatial features and TCNs distribution for the MATILDE regions, we used the following criteria:

Validity: Validity is directly related to the interpretation of data. Data are valid if they are able to match the intention of the question.

Availability: Availability refers to the assurance that data will continue to be collected and thus be available for other analyses in the future. In addition to that, availability concerns the physical capacity to access the data.

Reliability: Reliability refers to the extent to which we can rely on the source of the data and, therefore, the data itself. Reliability means that data are reasonably complete and accurate and meet the purpose.

Coverage: Coverage refers to both the geographic and temporal scope of the data collection.

The validity, availability, reliability, and the full coverage of consistent and harmonized data at the same territorial level, the same period, and the same measurement unit, with standardised methods of data production were determining the data sources. Based on these criteria, it was reasonable to use secondary data from international projects and databases. The following inventory gives an overview of available data sources:

- ESPON Databases: Regional Typologies, socioeconomic indicators
- OECD database for completing missing socioeconomic indicators
- ESPON PROFECY project for data on accessibility of basic services
- Eurostat regional database: It is the primary database for socioeconomic indicators. Key point for the selection of this database are the harmonised data of all countries.
- Eurostat - Geographic Information System of the Commission (GISCO) for NUTS 2006 and NUTS 2016: Degree of urbanisation, population grid and Regional Typologies
- Databases from the EU Science Hub, supported by the Joint research Centre and (JRC) and the DG for Regional and Urban Policy (DG REGIO) of the European Commission, together with the international partnership GEO Human Planet Initiative: open data on Population distribution for accessibility.

Some socio-demographic data and detailed data on Third Country Nationals were not available in a harmonised European-wide dataset, thus the project consortium had to conduct a collection from national statistical offices. This data collection was made through two steps. The first one consisted of a screening of available data regarding TCNs in each country by each project partner. The

information was collected, and the data availability was checked by period and territorial level by FAU to define the most appropriate one. The second step consisted in the effective data collection by each project partner.

The sources of each indicator can be found in the metadata sheet “Sources” of the Database. Data sources include third parties data, in particular those elaborated by the ESPON project PROFECY. In this case, the use and publication of data has been detailed in a Data Transfer Agreement between MATILDE coordinator and the ESPON PROFECY coordinator.

HARMONISATION OF THE TERRITORIAL LEVEL

After a first screening of available data, the NUTS 3 level resulted most appropriate for elaborating a harmonised dataset and have a common standard for the creation of thematic maps with GIS. Data on TCNs at LAU2- level were not focused on the course of elaborating D2.1 but will be collected in the further course of the project, especially within WP5.

The NUTS 3 regions for the elaboration of regional profiles were selected based on the location of case studies. Consequently, these 21 regions were defined as “MATILDE regions”. The following table shows the names of the NUTS 3 regions in the respective national language and the corresponding English names of the regions if existing. Additionally, the name of the respective NUTS 2 region is mentioned.

Region Number	English Name	NUTS 3 CODE	NUTS 3 NAME	NUTS 2 Region
1	South Tyrol	ITH10	Bolzano-Bozen	Bolzano
2.1	Berchtesgadener Land	DE215	Berchtesgadener Land	Oberbayern
2.2	Regen	DE229	Regen	Niederbayern
2.3	Neustadt an der Aisch	DE25A	Neustadt an der Aisch-Bad Windsheim	Mittelfranken
2.4	Oberallgäu	DE27E	Oberallgäu	Schwaben
2.5	Garmisch-Partenkirchen	DE21D	Garmisch-Partenkirchen	Oberbayern
3.1	Klagenfurt-Villach	AT211	Klagenfurt-Villach	Kärnten
3.2	Upper Carinthia	AT212	Oberkärnten	Kärnten
3.3	Lower Carinthia	AT213	Unterkärnten	Kärnten
4	Dalarna County	SE312	Dalarnas län	Norra Mellansverige
5	Metropolitan City of Turin	ITC11	Torino	Piemonte
6	North Karelia	FI1D3	Pohjois-Karjala	Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi
7	North Ayrshire	UKM93	East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland	South Western Scotland
8	Bursa	TR411	Bursa	Bursa
9.1	Bludenz-Bregenzerwald	AT341	Bludenz-Bregenzerwald	Vorarlberg
9.2	Rheintal-Bodenseegebiet	AT342	Rheintal-Bodenseegebiet	Vorarlberg
10	Ostrobothnia	FI195	Pohjanmaa	Länsi-Suomi
11	Haskovo	BG422	Haskovo	South Central Region
12.1	Oppland	NO021	Hedmark	Innlandet
12.2	Hedmark	NO022	Oppland	Innlandet
13	Huesca	ES241	Huesca	Aragón

Table 1: Names of MATILDE Regions and respective NUTS 2 regions

If data were not available at NUTS 3 level, but the indicator was important for the description of the economic structure of the region, data were collected on NUTS 2 level and adopted to the NUTS 3 regions. This was only possible in case of indicator with rational numbers, not absolute numbers. This procedure was applied to the indicators People at Risk of Poverty (%), Young people neither in employment nor in education and training (%), Population aged 25-64 with tertiary education (%) and Population aged 30-34 with tertiary education (%). It was also necessary in case of the indicator unemployment rate for the region TR411 – Bursa.

HARMONISATION OF THE PERIOD

The period 2008-2018 has proven to be adequate to provide the most complete dataset. Focusing on the selected decade 2008-2018, we were able to depict most current immigration processes in MATILDE regions, encompassing most recent immigration of humanitarian migrants in particular. For the previous period, following the 1990s, data often were not available among all MATILDE countries and regions and, thus, analyses had to be conducted by means of a literature review.

Small gaps in the period 2008-2018 of Eurostat data were completed by national statistical offices, which led to the problem of consistency of measurement units and data production method.

Nevertheless, some indicators were available only for a shorter time span:

- Demographic data on median age of population, old dependency ratio, young dependency ratio, and ageing index are only available from 2014-2018.
- The gross value added and employment by NACE sectors were not available for 2018 in all countries.
- The gross domestic product (GDP) was not available for 2018.
- The migration balance for 2018 was not available for Germany, thus the variable of the cumulative migration balance had to be calculated for 2008-2017.

CONSISTENCY OF MEASUREMENT UNITS

Gaps in the period 2008-2018 and missing data for certain regions in the Eurostat datasets were completed by national statistical offices. To gain a complete and harmonised dataset for each indicator, it is crucial that data from national statistical offices represent the same units of measurements. This is also related to problems in consistency of the data production method.

The **gross domestic product** (GDP) in purchasing power standard (PPS) per inhabitant are suitable for the comparison in single years among different regions.

To obtain the regional GDP growth rate, the GDP volume in Euro per inhabitant was used. Based on these data the real GDP was calculated in a first step by using national deflator from OECD, with the basic year 2015. In a second step, the annual average growth rate was calculated.

To distinguish the three economic sectors for the relative weight of the **gross value added** (GVA) and the **employment by sector**, the following categories according to the NACE Rev.2 classification was applied:

Primary sector:

- "A- Agriculture, forestry and fishing"

Secondary sector:

- "B-E - Industry (except construction)"
- "F - Construction"

Tertiary sector.

- "G-J - Wholesale and retail trade; transport; accommodation and food service activities; information and communication"
- "K-N - Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities; professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support service activities"
- "O-U - Public administration and defence; compulsory social security; education; human health and social work activities; arts, entertainment and recreation, repair of household goods and other services"

Unemployment rate

The OECD definitions correspond widely to those of the International Labour Organization (ILO) (OECD Library) and constituted the basis of the collection of this indicator. Data for the UK were collected according to ILO standards (Scottish Government 2018). Data for East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland (UKM93) 2008-2011 & 2018 represent an estimation collecting data from the local authorities North Ayrshire and East Ayrshire. The small discrepancy in population numbers compared to the NUTS 3 region, which does not contain the Isle of Arran had to be neglected. Although there was this minor problem with different administrative units, deviations only range from 0.6 to 1.5 percentage points with one single outlier of 2 percentage points. Data for 2017 and 2018 of Norway bases on the national Labour Force Survey and are within the range of previous years. Data for 2018 of Italy were collected from ISTAT. Since the most recent change of the survey method undertaken at the beginning of in 2004, the data are in line with European Union regulations (ISTAT 2020). As no ILO data for Austria 2009-2018 at NUTS 3 level were available, the NUTS 3 unemployment rate was estimated by taking the ILO federal state average (NUTS 2) and distribute it to the NUTS 3 level based on the structure of the results of the national methodology of Austria at NUTS 3 level. Missing data from Oberallgäu were completed by data from the Bavarian statistical office (*dt. "Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik"*), missing data form Finland by the survey "Population aged 15-74 by labour force status and region 2011-2019" of Statistics Finland.

Data on **risk of poverty** are based on the definition of Eurostat: "At risk-of-poverty are persons with an equivalised disposable income below the risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income (after social transfers)" (Eurostat 2019b). Large time spans were missing for Austria, Finland, Germany and Turkey. All recovered data in national statistical offices correspond to the threshold of 60% of the national median.

It was not possible to harmonize data for the indicator "**Early leavers from education and training**". Such data are available on Eurostat for the NUTS 2 level, but the big range of missing values in the MATILDE regions of Austria and the UK created insufficiency. Due to the different methodology of

surveys of Eurostat and the national statistical offices in UK and Austria regarding early school leavers, it was not possible to harmonize these data for the different MATILDE regions.

Data for the infrastructure dimension about **accessibility of selected basic services**, were collected based on the availability of all MATILDE regions. Because of missing data in Turkey within the ESPON PROFECY project, it was not possible to collect accessibility data for the services doctors and pharmacies.

DATA PROCESSING

For some needed indicators, an additional data processing predominantly with GIS software was required, for elaborating a comprehensive and harmonised dataset.

Data on **mountain typologies** were exported from the Eurostat Regions and Cities Illustrated (RCI) – online tool and updated to the publication “Methodological manual on territorial typologies” (Eurostat 2019a). This allowed us to extend the typology also to the whole area of interest, e.g. also Turkey, and getting an updated classification with population numbers of 2018. The update was made by entering the classifications for each missing region by drawing in Arc GIS software.

Data on **border typologies** were extracted from the Eurostat Regions and Cities Illustrated (RCI) – online tool and joined to the interested NUTS 3 regions. Some incongruent results required an update to the respective maps in the publication “Methodological manual on territorial typologies” by drawing in Arc GIS software.

To reveal the presence of **Functional Urban Areas** (FUA) in the respective MATILDE region, the shapefile of FUA was overlapped in GIS with the NUTS 3 regions.

The **share of population in rural areas** was extracted from the Eurostat Geographic Information System of the Commission (GISCO), which provides the Degree of Urbanisation (DEGURBA) dataset.

This dataset provides population data at municipal level (LAU 2 level) for 2018 and the classification of each municipality. To select the municipalities of each MATILDE region, the DEGURBA polygon shapefile was transferred to points in Arc GIS software. The points representing municipalities, which are located within the MATILDE regions were selected by the extract toolset “Clip” in ArcGIS software. To each of the resulted 1.098 municipalities it was added the information of the MATILDE region it belongs to. This made it possible to summarize the population of the municipalities classified as “rural” within each MATILDE region by a Pivot – table in Excel software.

The **share of agricultural land and forest areas** bases on the Corine Land Cover (CLC) raster dataset 2018 from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service with a resolution of 100 x 100m per pixel. Land Cover data were extracted for each MATILDE region by the raster processing tool “clip” in Arc GIS software, to receive separated raster attribute tables with the numbers of pixels (100x100m) of every land cover classification. Thus, every pixel represents 1ha surface. Corine Land Cover - Agricultural areas are composed of the of CLC classes 211 to 244: Non-irrigated arable land, permanently irrigated land, rice fields, vineyards, fruit trees and berry plantations, olive groves, pastures, annual crops associated with permanent crops, complex cultivation patterns, land principally occupied by agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation. Forests are composed of the classifications 311 to 313: Broad-leaved forest, Coniferous forest, Mixed forest.

The collection of information regarding **regions in industrial transition**, data from the ESPON regional typologies dataset of 2011 were transferred from NUTS 2006 to NUTS 2016. It was made by a geospatial analysis using the spatial join tool in Arc GIS software, overlapping NUTS 2016 as point features for each region and NUTS 2006 polygons, which contained the data. These data were previously joined from the Excel – file to the NUTS 2006 shapefile.

Travel times to services of general interest were provided from the ESPON PROFECY project for the complete coverage of the EU countries, also involving Turkey for most of the analysed services. It consists of a raster grid of 2,5 x 2,5 km in shapefile format, containing data for the services supermarkets, primary schools, secondary schools, hospitals and train stations. To receive a

comparable indicator for every NUTS 3 region, the average travel time by car to each service weighted by the population was calculated¹. For this calculation, the ESPON grid with information of travel times had to be combined with population data. For this processing it was used the GEOSTAT population grid 1 x 1 km (Eurostat GEOSTAT), which contains population numbers from 2011 for every square kilometre. Since Turkey is not covered by this population grid, it was necessary to use the population grid of the Global Human Settlement Layer 2015 (European Commission & Joint Research Centre) in raster format, named GHS-POP. The disadvantage for this dataset consists in big discrepancies compared to total population numbers of NUTS 3 region from Eurostat. The population grids were transformed to point data in shapefiles using Arc GIS software. The information of travel times on the polygon grid were joined to the point data by a spatial join. Additionally, it was joined the information of the MATILDE region it belongs to. With this data table it was possible to calculate the weighted average travel time of the service in each MATILDE region.

$$x = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (TT_i \times Pop_i)}{Pop_{MATreg}}$$

x... weighted average travel time of the service in the MATILDE region

Pop... Population in the pixel *i*

TT... Travel time by car in the pixel

Pop_{MATreg}... Total population of the MATILDE region

The **share of population living in peripheral municipalities** is based on the classification of peripheral municipalities by the ESPON PROFECY project. The respective shapefile was clipped by the shapefile of MATILDE regions using Arc GIS software. The resulted areas were intersected with the population data of 2018 from the DEGURBA classification at municipal level. This made it possible to gain a data table for the municipalities with the information on the peripheral

¹ A further description of the decision to use this method contains Deliverable D2.1 “analysing the performance of MATILDE regions: territorial and socio-economic indicators”

classification, the population number and to which MATILDE region the municipality belongs to. Based on this data table, the number of people living in peripheral areas for each MATILDE region was summarized.

Missing data in the time periods of the indicators “risk of poverty”, “unemployment rate” and “young people neither in employment nor in education and training” were generating missing values for the variable 2008-2018 for some regions. These missing values were substituted to generate a complete set of variables for all regions to elaborate the classification of the regions.

Change in percent of people at risk of poverty in percentage points (RiskPo_Diff_08-18):

- Bursa (TR411) calculated by the period 2014-2018.
- For East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland (UKM93) no input data were available.

Change in unemployment rate in percentage points (Unempl_Diff_08-18):

- For Dalarnas län (SE312) and Huesca, (ES241), values from 2008 to 2017 were used, instead of 2008-2018.

Change in percent of NEETs in percentage points (Diff_NEETS):

- For Regen (DE229) data from 2008 to 2016 were used.
- For Vorarlberg (AT341 and AT342) data from 2008 to 2017 were used.
- For East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland (UKM93) data from 2013 to 2018 were used.
- For Hedmark (NO021) and Oppland (NO022) data from 2008 to 2016 were used.

2.2 CREATION OF THE DATABASE

The table database on spatial features and TCNs distribution was created in Excel -format. Data have been joined at the basis of NUTS 3 regions, NUTS 2 regions and country level. To facilitate the selection of the respective regions e.g. from downloaded Eurostat spreadsheets, is has been used “index” and “match” formulas in Excel.

The Geodatabase was created as a File-Geodatabase with Arc GIS software containing the processed geographical data, including polygon features, point feature (former shapefiles) as well as a raster dataset (former .TIF-files).

Data coding consisted of re-classifying the data into a form that facilitates the analysis and prepares the data for processing with statistical software or GIS software.

The codes for missing data in the table database were encoded with “n/a”, for the geodatabase with “-999”.

The structure of the provided metadata is based on an example of the ESPON M4D Project in 2012, which was used as a template. Therefore, it is in line with the INSPIRE directive.

2.3 STRUCTURE OF THE MATILDE DATABASE

The two parts of the database, i.e. the table database and the geodatabase, are complementing each other. Geodata are the basis for the elaboration of indicators at NUTS 3 level for the territorial and infrastructure dimension, while the table database describes metadata on sources and indicators also for the geodatabase and collects all calculated variables.

STRUCTURE OF THE TABLE DATABASE

The table database consists of sheets for metadata and data. The metadata information had to be split up into four sheets:

- The “Dataset description” contains a general information on the project, contact persons, use constraints and abbreviations
- The “Index” is a list of the code and name of the indicators, with a link to the sheet for better navigation, separated according to the three dimensions, TCNs data and variables
- The “Indicator description” contains the name, code, years available, methodology or formula, use constraints, and spatial binding of each indicator, as well as the respective variable description
- “Sources” contains the provider name, the reference, the copyright, the publication title, and the URL of each indicator separated according to the three dimensions, TCNs data and aggregated indicators.

In the sheet “ALL Variables NUTS 3” contains all calculated variables at NUTS 3 level for the 21 MATILDE regions, which represents the basis for building categories in D2.1 and the elaboration of the D2.4 MATRIX (Compilation of indicators to analyse social, economic and territorial impacts).

All other sheets contain the raw data for each indicator on each level, together with the calculated variable in a separate column.

STRUCTURE OF THE GEODATABASE:

The Geodatabase “DB on spatial features and TCNs distribution.gdb” consists of feature classes structured by four thematic fields, or rather “dimensions”. The dimension A “MATILDE Regions” defines the delineation of the selected NUTS 3 Regions. Part B contains data for the territorial dimension, part C for the infrastructure dimension and part D contains data on TCNs.

All feature classes are clipped to the delineation of MATILDE Regions, except the regional typologies at NUTS 3 level, which have an extent for whole Europe (see B1-B4).

Dimension	Feature class description	Name of the feature class
A: MATILDE Regions	Delineation of the MATILDE regions	A_MATILDE_Regions
B: Territorial dimension	Urban – Rural – Typology	B1_URBAN_RURAL_NUTS3_3035
	Mountain regions:	B2_Mountain_regions_2018
	Border regions	B3_Border_regions_2018
	Regions in industrial transition	B4_IndTrans_2006
	Corine Land Cover	B5_CorineLandCover_MATILDE_reg
	DEGURBA classification	B6_DEGURBA_2018_MATReg
	DEGURBA classification with information about the belonging of the MATILDE region	B7_DEGURBA_2018_MATReg_pt_info
	Population density in Bursa	B8_Bursa_TR_2011_LAU2
C: Infra-structure dimension	Population living in municipalities, classified as inner peripheries	C1_GEOSTAT_POP_IPs_LAU2_MATReg_Pt
	Population and travel times to selected services of general interest	C2_GEOSTAT_POP_TT_SGI_NUTS3_MATReg_Pt
	Population and travel times to selected services of general interest in Bursa:	C3_GHS_POP_TT_SGI_Bursa_Pt
D: TCNs	Data on the distribution of Third Country Nationals	D1_TCNs_MatReg

Table 2: Content of the geodatabase

3. DATA MANAGEMENT AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

3.1 DATA STORAGE

The databases are stored at the Eurac Research IT infrastructure for 7 years after the end of the duration of the project. It is accessible for the Eurac Research Institute for Regional Development. EURAC is ISO27001 certified, and will guarantee the availability, confidentiality and integrity of the data.

As defined in the project, data will be made available to the public by December 2020. The proposal in the MATILDE Data Management Plan (Deliverable 2.1) is to make data available through the platform Zenodo.

Timeframe:

The databases are stored from December 2020, at the deadline of the deliverable Deliverable 2.2.

Formats

According to the MATILDE data management plan, file format obsolescence must be prevented. Therefore, we selected file formats, that have a high chance of remaining usable in the far future:

- The table database is stored as Excel spreadsheet (.xlsx).
- The Geodatabase is stored in (.gdb) format.

Both file formats are commonly used and have open specifications, but they are not independent of specific software. However, the respective software for these formats are commonly used. Geodatabases are also accessible with Quantum GIS software, a free and Open Source Geographic Information System. (QGIS).

3.2 DATA USAGE

The data will be **shared with partners** in August 2020, after data quality check has been carried out by Eurac Research together with FAU. In terms of access to data, the MATILDE database will be made available to project partners from August 2020, available on the project internal cloud space set up on Microsoft Teams. In the case of scientific/dissemination publications, it is necessary to consult all relevant Work Package members and data providers (i.e. Case Study teams) as potential authors. It is the choice of the data provider to decide whether or not to participate in the publication and to authorize the use of data. The data can be used if authorized by the provider, always acknowledging the relevant contributors. If data providers do not authorize the use of the data, these cannot be used. The aim of sharing data within the MATILDE consortium is to facilitate the dissemination of data via scientific publications: since these will require a considerable amount of this to be developed, an early sharing with partners allows them to have the time to examine and analyse the data provided in Database 2.2, and to elaborate proposals for scientific publications that draw on these data.

The data will be **shared with the public** at the end of December 2020, with the aim to make them publicly accessible as these represent the data underpinning publications released within the project (e.g., Deliverable 2.1).

The data will be also **shared with stakeholders**, in order to provide evidence for policy recommendations and governance solutions elaborated within the project.

3.3 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

To protect the intellectual property of the Consortium and its partners, data were managed in line with the Grant Agreement (Section 3), the Consortium Agreement (Sections 8 and 9), and the MATILDE Data Management Plan (D1.3).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The MATILDE database is a repository of processed and harmonised secondary stock data at a common territorial level, used for the elaborations of classifications of the investigated regions and the migration impact assessment.

It was not possible to harmonise very important data on socio-demographic features and TCNs at municipal level (LAU2), which would have been more appropriate for the analysis of the distribution of TCNs, at this stage. In the further course of the MATILDE project, efforts on data collection on local level will be continued and it will be evaluated if a common European standard would be helpful to resolve this problem.

Despite the local level, also on the regional level, we were not able to find or harmonise all necessary data on TCNs for the MATILDE regions in Bulgaria, Turkey, Finland, and Sweden. Therefore, we recommend establishing a harmonised European-wide procedure for collecting data on TCNs. For this purpose, common understanding between national statistical offices have to be developed, being aware that national policies, e.g. naturalisation policies, often hamper such efforts. However, a collection in a Eurostat regional database on socioeconomic indicators would facilitate the data collection.

METADATA OF THE GEODATABASE

Dataset information	
Name	Spatial features and TCNs distribution
Project	H2020 MATILDE
Creation date	22/07/2020
Abstract	This dataset contains data for the delineation of the MATILDE regions (A) for the territorial dimension (B) and indicators for accessibility (C) for the classification of MATILDE Regions. Dimension D consists of data on Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in the respective regions.
Topic Category	Society; Economic activities, conditions and employment
Keywords	Social aspects, population: demography, rural population, human migration; economic structure; mountainous area
Lineage	This dataset was produced within the MATILDE project.
Resource Type	Spatial data set series, Geodatabase (.gdb)
Dataset Language	Eng
Metadata Language	Eng
Metadata date	22/07/2020
Temporal Extent	2008-2018
Organization Name	Eurac Research - Institute for Regional Development
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Phone	+39 0471 055 300
Use constraint	<i>copyright (default)</i>
Access condition	<i>No conditions apply (default)</i>
Other constraints	<i>The dataset has no limitations, except the use of data on the accessibility dimension, which come from the ESPON PROFECY project. These data are only available on request.</i>
Access classification	<i>unclassified</i>

Feature Class description	
Title	A_MATILDE_Regions
Abstract	This feature class contains the polygons of the delineation for the MATILDE regions.
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89_LAEA_Europe
Years available	2016
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	NUTS
Nomenclature Level	3
Nomenclature Version	2016
Source description	
Provider Name	Eurostat
Reference	Eurostat 2019: GISCO - Geographical Information and maps. Geodata. Reference data. Administrative units.
Copyright	©Eurostat
Publication Title	NUTS 2016

Feature Class description	
Title	B1_URBAN_RURAL_NUTS3_3035
Abstract	This feature class contains the polygons of NUTS3 regions with information on the Urban - rural - Typology
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89_LAEA_Europe
Years available	2018
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	Europe
Nomenclature Name	NUTS
Nomenclature Level	3
Nomenclature Version	2016

Feature Class description	
Title	B2_Mountain_regions_2018
Abstract	This feature class contains information regarding the mountain typology, separated by 4 categories.
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89
Years available	2018
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	Europe
Nomenclature Name	NUTS
Nomenclature Level	3
Nomenclature Version	2016

Feature Class description	
Title	B3_Border_regions_2018
Abstract	This feature class contains information if a NUTS 3 region have population within 25 km of a national land border.
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89
Years available	2018
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	Europe
Nomenclature Name	NUTS
Nomenclature Level	3
Nomenclature Version	2016

Feature Class description	
Title	B4_IndTrans_2006
Abstract	Industrial regions in transition are those regions where the share of GVA and employment has changed between two points in time.
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89_LAEA_Europe
Years available	2011
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	Europe
Nomenclature Name	NUTS
Nomenclature Level	3
Nomenclature Version	2016

Feature Class description	
Title	B5_CorineLandCover_MATILDE_reg
Abstract	This raster dataset contains data from the Corine Land Cover dataset of the EEA, clipped by the MATILDE regions.
Spatial representation type	Raster
CRS	ETRS_1989_LAEA
Years available	
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	Raster
Nomenclature Level	100 x 100 m
Nomenclature Version	-

Feature Class description	
Title	B6_DEGURBA2018_MATReg
Abstract	<p>This feature class contains information on the Degree of Urbanisation and population numbers in the respective municipality. Classes are divided by 3 categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cities (Densely populated areas: at least 50 % of the population lives in urban centres) - Towns and suburbs (Intermediate density areas: less than 50 % of the population lives in rural areas and cities) - Rural areas (Thinly populated areas: > 50 % of the population lives in rural areas)
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	GCS_ETRS_1989
Years available	2018
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	LAU
Nomenclature Level	2
Nomenclature Version	2018

Feature Class description	
Title	B7_DEGURBA_2018_MATReg_pt_att
Abstract	<p>This feature class on municipal level contains information on the Degree of Urbanisation and the belonging to the MATILDE region. The point location are the centroid of the municipalities.</p>
Spatial representation type	Vector (point)
CRS	GCS_ETRS_1989
Years available	2018
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	LAU
Nomenclature Level	2
Nomenclature Version	2018

Feature Class description	
Title	B8_Bursa_TR_2011_LAU2
Abstract	Population numbers and population density on municipal level in the province of Bursa.
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89_LAEA_Europe
Years available	2011
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	Bursa, Turkey
Nomenclature Name	LAU
Nomenclature Level	2
Nomenclature Version	2011
Source description	
Provider Name	Eurostat
Reference	LAU1- boundaries and Population: European Commission/Eurostat/ NUTS - Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics/Local Administrative Units (LAU). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/local-administrative-units
Copyright	Eurostat
Publication Title	Geodata. Shapefiles (EL, IE, TR). TR_2011_LAU2_ETRS89.shp:

Feature Class description	
Title	C1_GEOSTAT_POP_IPs_LAU2_MatReg_Pt
Abstract	This feature class presents the population distribution by point features for every 1 x 1 km grid cell, in municipalities classified as peripheral by the ESPON PROFECY project. The information on the MATILDE region is joined.
Spatial representation type	Vector (point)
CRS	ETRS_1989_LAEA
Years available	Population: 2011, Travel times 2016
Use constraint	Restricted
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	Grid
Nomenclature Level	1 x 1 km
Nomenclature Version	2011

Feature Class description	
Title	C2_GEOSTAT_POP_TT_SGI_NUTS3_MatReg_Pt
Abstract	This feature class presents the population distribution by point - features for every 1 x 1 km grid cell and the respective travel time to services of general interest.
Spatial representation type	Vector (point)
CRS	ETRS_1989_LAEA
Years available	Population: 2011, Travel times 2016
Use constraint	Restricted
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	Grid
Nomenclature Level	1 x 1 km
Nomenclature Version	2011

Feature Class description	
Title	C3_GHS_POP_TT_SGI_Bursa_Pt
Abstract	This feature class presents the population distribution by point – features for every 1 x 1 km grid cell in the Bursa province and the respective travel time to services of general interest.
Spatial representation type	Vector (point)
CRS	ETRS_1989_LAEA
Years available	Population: 2015, Travel times 2016
Use constraint	Restricted
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	Bursa, Turkey
Nomenclature Name	Grid
Nomenclature Level	1 x 1 km
Nomenclature Version	2015

Feature Class description	
Title	D1_TCNs_MatReg
Abstract	The feature class contains data on TCNs on NUTS 3 level for 18 MATILDE regions. Indicators are explained in the table database.
Spatial representation type	Vector (polygon)
CRS	ETRS89_LAEA_Europe
Years available	2008-2017
Use constraint	Copyright
Spatial Binding	
Geographic Location	MATILDE regions
Nomenclature Name	NUTS
Nomenclature Level	3
Nomenclature Version	2016